

RECONSTRUCTION OF UKRAINE AS RECOVERY MARKET.

Dr. Olena Lesyk-Laikari, University of Helsinki 2024

This report touches on, among other things, the following topics of interest to Finnish companies:

- British architectural design
- Polish architectural firms
- Austrian hospital design
- Investments in Ukraine's paper and wood-processing industries, supported by the Netherlands
- Dutch drone companies operating in Ukraine
- The Danish operating model
- Croatian and Slovenian demining expertise
- British companies interested in the Ukrainian market

The European Investment Bank estimates that Ukraine's reconstruction will require more than USD 1,000 billion in public and private capital. Adjusted for inflation, this sum is more than five times larger than the United States' Marshall Plan aid to Europe after World War II.

Ukraine has stated that its goal is for 60% of the labor in reconstruction projects to be carried out by Ukrainian companies.

Ukraine has also assessed which building materials could be produced domestically in order to reduce imports. These include bricks, concrete, paints, and ceramic tiles. Glass, electrical equipment, and elevators, however, are expected to remain imported products.

Below is a brief overview of what reconstruction currently looks like:

Since the start of the war, more than 30 industrial investment projects have been launched in Ukraine. Most are located in Western Ukraine.

The Czech Republic has been one of Ukraine's most visible supporters, particularly in recent

times. It has also taken a dynamic, hands-on approach to reconstruction. In addition to dozens of Czech companies already operating in Ukraine, the country has brought large business delegations to Ukraine, with participants representing especially the energy, healthcare, and transport sectors.

The Czech Model

The Czech Republic also differs from many other countries in how it helps companies enter the market. While many countries e.g. Denmark, focused on bilateral aid directed at one large target, the Czech government funds smaller projects from its own budget, enabling companies to build references. Through pilot projects, companies gain experience operating in Ukraine, and these references make it easier for them to succeed in tenders for larger, internationally funded projects. Is this a strategy Finland should also consider?

The Czech government actively works to build direct business connections for its companies and has formed various alliances with other countries. Together with South Korean partners, Czech companies, including Linet and Royax, are involved in a broad medical support program that will result, among other things, in a training center in Lviv.

The Czech Republic has supplied arms to Ukraine with funding from Denmark, the Netherlands, and the United States. The scale of these efforts is illustrated by the fact that since the war began, the Czech Republic has granted export licenses to Ukraine worth nearly EUR 5 billion.

CSG, Czechoslovak Group, one of Europe's largest arms manufacturers, is currently planning to build a factory in Ukraine together with Ukroboronprom.

Major International Investments

Bayer AG, Germany has announced investments of EUR 60 million in seed production in Ukraine. According to Bayer Ukraine CEO Oliver Gierlichs, production from the new facility will serve both the domestic market and exports.

Rheinmetall AG announced in February plans to establish a joint venture in Ukraine with the state-owned Ukrainian Defence Industry JSC to produce much-needed 155 mm artillery ammunition.

Flensburger Fahrzeugbau has delivered 700 armored vehicles to Ukraine and has begun building a maintenance company in Ukraine with a local partner.

By October 2023, Germany had granted EUR 280 million in guarantees for 14 investment projects in Ukraine. A further 30 projects were under evaluation, with 70 more in the

pipeline. While this sounds large compared to Finland, it is worth noting that over 2,000 German companies operated in Ukraine before the war—so Finland has significant ground to make up. (Finnvera has stated it will soon disclose its Ukraine guarantees, which will provide a clearer picture of Finland’s activity level.)

Steel, Infrastructure, and Materials

Ukraine’s largest steel producer Metinvest estimates that once large-scale reconstruction begins, Ukraine will require 3.5 million tonnes of steel annually over 5–10 years for housing and infrastructure repairs, by comparison, Finland uses 300,000–400,000 tonnes per year. The company says it is ready to meet this demand.

“Our approach is that we must do something now. We cannot wait for the war to end and reconstruction conferences to be held.”

Fixit Gruppe AG, Switzerland is building a new construction materials plant in Western Ukraine; construction has already begun.

Waagner-Biro Bridge Systems, Austria has started production of modular steel bridges in Western Ukraine. According to CEO Richard Kerschbaumer, “there will be work for decades.”

Denmark, the Baltics, and Regional Support

Denmark has donated EUR 120 million for the reconstruction of Mykolaiv, largely used for generators, water pumps, heaters, and mine clearance. Danish consultants and local authorities are now preparing a master plan extending to the 2050s.

Lithuania has focused its aid on areas near Kyiv, including Borodyanka, where Lithuanian companies have built a kindergarten, repaired schools, and constructed a bridge in Irpin.

Estonia has concentrated its bilateral aid on the Zhytomyr region and plays a major role in digitalizing Ukrainian society.

Turkey, Romania, and Poland

Turkish construction companies have completed 70 projects worth around USD 1 billion during the two years of war. Firms such as Onur Group and Dogus Construction are rebuilding roads, bridges, and hospitals and positioning themselves for larger contracts.

Romania has become a critical logistics hub, particularly through the port of Constanta, supported by EUR 126 million in EU funding. Since the war began, trade between Romania and Ukraine has more than doubled, and 775 Ukrainian companies have expanded into Romania.

Poland is often described as the hub of Ukraine's reconstruction:

600 Polish companies currently operate in Ukraine

26,900 Ukrainian-owned companies operate in Poland

2,000 additional Polish companies have expressed interest in reconstruction

Polish banks estimate reconstruction could boost Poland's GDP by 3.8%.

Austria, Italy, the UK, the Netherlands, Nordics

Austria remains one of Ukraine's largest historical investors, with 200 Austrian-owned companies employing around 20,000 Ukrainians. Major players include Kronospan, Wienerberger, Strabag, OMV, and Raiffeisen Bank, though political tensions have cooled relations.

Italy is Ukraine's second-largest export market, and Italian companies are involved in steel, infrastructure, and the reconstruction of Odesa.

The UK enjoys strong goodwill in Ukraine. Norman Foster and Arup have already begun planning the reconstruction of Kharkiv, estimated at EUR 8 billion.

The Netherlands has established one of Europe's most generous support schemes for reconstruction, the Ukraine Partnership Facility, offering 100% grants for projects worth EUR 500,000–5 million. Dutch companies are particularly active in water technology, healthcare, food quality, and ISR drone technology.

Sweden, Norway, and other Nordic countries maintain strong commercial and aid ties, with Norway alone committing EUR 7 billion over five years under its Nansen Programme.

Looking Ahead: Finland's Position

Future analysis will focus on opportunities for Finnish companies in Ukraine, considering questions such as:

Do Finnish companies already have trade relationships or deep Ukraine expertise?

Does Finland have a special status as a supporter of Ukraine that could translate into commercial advantages?

Will Finland target significant bilateral aid to specific regions, as Denmark has done?

Do Finnish companies have access to an ecosystem that supports market entry?

Does experience in Russia prepare companies for Ukraine's reconstruction market—a claim made primarily in Finland?

The goal is to identify how Finnish companies should approach the Ukrainian market, which sectors or niches may offer opportunities, and how market development should be carried out in practice.